

1 Investigation of Static/Dynamic Moduli and Plastic Response of Shale Specimens

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3 ABSTRACT

4 High clay and organic content, irregular voids, presence of micro-cracks, and obvious bedding
5 planes are among features of shale gas rocks that affect their mechanical response. These
6 sedimentary rocks exhibit substantial degree of anisotropy and inhomogeneity, with non-linear
7 response when subjected to axial loading. The laboratory characterization of these rocks is
8 necessary to design an optimized hydraulic fracturing programme, and for reliable constitutive
9 and numerical modeling of these formations. In this study, a series of triaxial multi-stage elastic
10 and cyclic tests were performed on Marcellus Shale specimens, retrieved from a deep well (~2270
11 m deep) located in West Virginia, to characterize their elastic-plastic and hysteresis response
12 subjected to loading/unloading cycles. The experimental results indicated a nonlinear response,
13 particularly at low differential stress levels. In addition, the specimens with higher clay content
14 exhibited a softer response with lower estimated static and dynamic moduli at different stress
15 levels compared to those of specimens with higher calcite/quartz content. The ultrasonic P- and
16 S-wave velocity measurements were found to be sensitive to the changes in the micro-structure
17 of the rock caused by variation in stress condition. In general, the estimated Young's modulus
18 during unloading was found to be higher than loading. The plastic deformations were pronounced
19 in the first cycle of loading, followed by a decreasing trend in the subsequent cycles.

20

21 KEYWORDS

22 elastic, multi-stage triaxial, hysteresis, pressure-dependent, dynamic, ultrasonic velocity

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23 INTRODUCTION

24 According to [1], there are more than 39 billion barrels of proved oil/gas reservoirs, the highest
25 since 1972. Unconventional oil/gas resources such as shale gas and tight oil are significantly
26 contributing to the oil/gas production [1]. Shale gas reservoirs have been exploited with a total
27 technically-recoverable resources of about 660 trillion cubic feet [1] around the globe in countries
28 such as China, United States, Mexico, South Africa, and Australia to name a few [2,3]. In the
29 United States, development of Barnett, Haynesville, Marcellus, and Utica Shale among others
30 has led to increased interest in evaluating properties of shale gas formations [1].

31 Shale/clayey rocks, categorized into clastic sedimentary rock [e.g. 3], usually contain very fine
32 grains resulting in very low permeability, and therefore, extraction of natural gas from these
33 organic-rich rocks requires creation of fractures in the reservoir via hydraulic fracturing [e.g. 4,5].
34 Despite recent advancements in understanding of the mechanics of hydraulic fracturing, the
35 outcome of hydraulic fracturing operation, and also the fracture closure over time are variable and
36 unpredictable in different shale/clayey formations [3,6-9]. This is, in part, due to lack of knowledge
37 about the shale rock properties controlling the fracture initiation, propagation, and closure under
38 reservoir conditions [7,10,11]. In order to optimize the required energy for hydraulic fracturing
39 operation and production in shale gas reservoirs, it is important to evaluate both elastic-plastic
40 and visco-elastic-plastic behavior of these rocks [12-15].

41 Shale/clayey rocks are typically recognized by their extremely low porosity and permeability [16-
42 18], with a wide range of mineralogy and Total Organic Content (TOC), and are highly
43 heterogeneous and anisotropic [7,11,19]. These characteristics significantly affect the outcome
44 of hydraulic fracturing during stimulation stage and fracture closure during production stage in a
45 shale gas reservoir [e.g. 20]. For example, during hydraulic fracturing, shale/clayey formations
46 with higher clay content, exhibit a more ductile behavior, and therefore tend to deform instead of
47 shattering [3,21].

48 The presence of clay/organic matters in shale/clayey formations results in significant visco-elastic
49 deformations, which in turn, affect both short- and long-term deformation of these formations
50 [5,8,21-23]. Time-dependent (i.e. visco-elastic) deformations might lead to change in the state of
51 the stress, elastic and failure characteristics, and permeability of shale/clayey rocks [9,17,24]. Liu
52 et al. [15] studied the effects of mineralogical composition, relative humidity, confining pressure,
53 and structural anisotropy on creep response of resaturated and desaturated Cox claystone

54 specimens and reported that active clay minerals significantly influence the creep strains. Liu et
55 al. [18] found that structural anisotropy significantly influences the creep response of Cox argillite
56 specimens, with increased strength due to visco-elastic-plastic deformations. Burgers' and
57 Power-Law models have shown to be able to reasonably capture the long-term creep response
58 of shale rocks [e.g. 8,22,24].

59 Laboratory characterization of shale rock specimens typically includes non-destructive and
60 destructive petrophysical and geomechanical testing [e.g. 25,26]. Elastic moduli (including
61 Young's and shear moduli and Poisson's ratio), strength properties (i.e. cohesion, coefficient of
62 internal friction, and unconfined compressive strength), hysteresis behavior (i.e. plastic
63 deformation), and creep response are important to be addressed for geomechanical
64 characterization of these shale formations [7,8,11,19,22]. Typically, these characteristics can be
65 determined in laboratory by performing triaxial experiments in drained/undrained conditions, and
66 by measurements of ultrasonic wave velocities at different stress conditions [e.g. 7,11,22]. Both
67 geomechanical and petrophysical properties are important for the optimized design of hydraulic
68 fracturing stimulation programme, and improved accuracy of production models.

69 Shale rocks are reported to be highly-nonlinear material [e.g. 7,11,19,22] with presence of micro-
70 cracks, that affect their elastic properties, particularly at lower confining levels of up to ~10 MPa
71 [e.g. 14,16,26]. Moreover, fabric anisotropy and composition are reported to have a substantial
72 influence on elastic moduli [7,26-28], resulting in higher degree of pressure-dependency of
73 stiffness compared to other rocks [e.g. 11,22]. Furthermore, shale rocks exhibit significant
74 variations in the measured static moduli during loading/unloading/reloading [7,11]. In addition,
75 irrecoverable deformations make it difficult to interpret the static moduli as elastic properties [e.g.
76 14,22].

77 In shale reservoirs, due to creep deformation, the created fractures gradually close under in-situ
78 stresses [e.g. 17,18]. In order to maintain continued reservoir production, it is necessary to re-
79 stimulate the reservoir. The response of shale rocks subjected to cyclic loading is more complex
80 compared to other rocks due to their inherent fabric complexity. These rocks show a brittle,
81 nonlinear, and highly-anisotropic plastic response as well as initiation of micro-cracks under
82 successive loading/unloading cycles, which affect their stiffness and strength properties [e.g.
83 19,29,30]. The permanent plastic deformations and degradation of elastic moduli due to fatigue
84 of shale formations play a significant role in design and operation of re-stimulation process [e.g.
85 31].

86 Ultrasonic wave propagation is often used to estimate the elastic properties of the rocks, referred
87 to as dynamic moduli. Typically, the estimated dynamic moduli are higher than the corresponding
88 static ones [e.g. 32,33]. The propagation of ultrasonic waves in rocks depends on volume,
89 geometry, and distribution of pores and fractures [34-38]. In a triaxial test, usually during isotropic
90 compression (hydrostatic stage), the ultrasonic velocities increase, however, during triaxial stage,
91 the ultrasonic velocities show an increasing/decreasing trend [e.g. 27,39,40].

92 In general, shale rocks exhibit irregular intergranular spaces as void [41], and high compressibility
93 due to high clay content [e.g. 24]. During hydrostatic and triaxial stages, shear and compressional
94 wave velocities can be affected by closure of existing micro-cracks, potential porosity reduction,
95 and creation of new micro-cracks [e.g. 42-45]. For low porosity shale specimens, typically by
96 increasing the mean stress, the P- and S-wave velocities monotonically increase during
97 hydrostatic stage followed by subsequent decrease during triaxial stages [e.g. 40]. It is worth
98 noting that ultrasonic wave velocities are significantly affected by: (i) the type of pore fluid [33], (ii)
99 the level of saturation [e.g. 46,47], and (iii) the orientation of bedding planes with respect to applied
100 differential stress [25,48]. It should be mentioned that in shales, existing/created fractures impact
101 the transmitted waves by: (i) filtering high frequency content of the wave, and (ii) attenuating the
102 signal [49].

103 Although several studies are available on geomechanical characterization of different shale
104 formations [e.g. 7,8,19,30], very limited studies are available on Marcellus Shale [e.g. 11,22,50].
105 Given that Marcellus Shale is the largest shale formation in the United States, and there is an
106 increasing demand for fundamental rock properties of this formation, this study focused on
107 characterization of Marcellus Shale specimens retrieved from a deep well. This study reports the
108 results from a set of multi-stage elastic and cyclic experiments on Marcellus Shale specimens, in
109 attempt to characterize the elastic-plastic properties of the specimens. The time-dependent and
110 strength properties of the shale specimens were investigated by performing creep and multi-stage
111 failure tests on the specimens, and the results are reported in a companion manuscript by the
112 authors.

113 Section 2 provides the information about the rock specimens used in this study, Section 3
114 discusses the experimental methodology, Section 4 presents the results followed by analysis and
115 discussion in Section 5. Finally, the conclusions of this study are provided in Section 6.

116 **2. MATERIALS**

117 The shale plugs (4 inches in diameter) were provided by West Virginia Geological and Economic
118 Survey. As part of the Department of Energy Eastern shale gas program, one of the cored wells
119 (EGSP West Virginia well #6) focused on Marcellus shale in Monongalia county, located in
120 Morgantown, West Virginia (Figure 1(a)). The cores had abundant disc fractures [51] and were
121 stored at room temperature and ambient humidity conditions. The cores were oriented
122 perpendicular to the bedding (Figure 1(b) and 1(c)). Although it was desired to retrieve several
123 1.5-inch diameter sub-cores (both perpendicular and parallel to the bedding for anisotropy
124 characterization) with aspect ratio close to 2, and despite the precautionary measures taken to
125 avoid breaking the plugs while coring them, due to the brittle nature of the plugs, it was only
126 possible to retrieve four sub-cores.

127 The specimens were drilled in the vertical direction, perpendicular to bedding planes as it can be
128 seen from Figures 1(c) and 1(d). Table 1 summarizes the information about the depth, dimensions
129 of the retrieved specimens, and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis. Figures 1(e) and 1(f) show the
130 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images, indicating presence of different features such as
131 micro-cracks sub-parallel to bedding, voids and inclusions. As it can be seen from Table 1, R1
132 and R2 specimens are rich in calcite/quartz, whereas, R3 and R4 specimens are rich in clay.
133 The TOC was determined as 2.7% using sample combustion method [52]. Using the comparison
134 between average grain density and the bulk density of the specimen [53], the porosity of the
135 specimens were estimated as 6%. Due to brittle nature of these shale specimens, and the lack of
136 information about the chemical composition of in-situ pore fluid, no attempt was made to re-
137 hydrate the specimens at different saturation levels.

138 **3. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY**

139 **3.1. Specimen Preparation**

140 ASTM D4543 Standard [54] was followed for preparation of rock core specimens. The two ends
141 of the specimens were lapped to 0.001 inch/inch to avoid local bending and non-uniform loading,
142 particularly during triaxial stage. Copper jacket was wrapped around the specimen, and the two
143 overlapping ends were soldered and smoothed (Figure 2(a)) to prevent the leakage of the
144 confining fluid into the jacket and consequently into the specimen during triaxial testing. The
145 wrapped copper jacket also facilitated attachment of the strain gauges (Figure 2(b)). Then, the
146 Viton jackets were attached to the two ends of the copper-jacketed specimen. Moreover, as an

147 additional layer of protection against leakage of the confining oil into the specimen, epoxy was
148 also added on the seam of the copper jacket.

149 Two sets of axial and radial strain gauges were attached on the copper jacket using high-
150 pressure-resistant epoxy as shown in Figure 2(c). These pairs of strain gauges were placed 90
151 degree with respect to each other, which allowed studying potential anisotropic nature in the
152 horizontal plane. Couplant was then added at the interface between the rock specimen and the
153 ultrasonic core-holder. Subsequently, the test column was prepared by wire tightening one end
154 of the Vitton jacket to the rock specimen and the other end to the ultrasonic core holder (Figure
155 2(c)). The test column was then mounted on the base plug (Figure 2(c)) to be inserted in the test
156 vessel, as shown in Figure 2(e).

157 **3.2. Experimental Procedure**

158 AutoLab 1500 instrument, a high-pressure fully servo-controlled triaxial equipment capable of
159 applying Confining Pressure (CP) of up to 70 MPa, Pore Pressures (P_P) of up to 70 MPa, and
160 Differential Stress (DS) of up to 580 MPa (for 1.5-inch diameter specimens), was used in this
161 study to perform the mechanical characterization of shale specimens (Figure 2(d)). The loading
162 piston in the upper chamber of the test vessel is equipped with a Linear Variable Differential
163 Transformer (LVDT) that allows (i) continuous monitoring of the specimen's axial displacement,
164 and (ii) verifying the measurements of axial strain gauges. In addition, a load cell placed in the
165 upper chamber of the test vessel measures the applied differential load to the specimen. The
166 instrument allows performing experiments under stress- and strain-control modes.

167 The ultrasonic transducers embeded in the top and bottom core holders (Figure 2(e)) allow
168 sending and receiving ultrasonic P-wave and cross-polarized S-wave waves (perpendicular to the
169 bedding planes) during triaxial testing of the specimens. The pulse generator, manufactured by
170 New England Research (NER) Inc., generates pulses with frequency of 10 pulses per second.
171 The P- and cross polarized S-wave transducers, manufactured by NER, had a central frequency
172 of 750 kHz. The ultrasonic waves acquisition rate was set at 10 pulses per second. Tektronix
173 TDS 3000 Series Oscilloscope was used as digitizer. For estimation of P- and S-wave velocities
174 (V_p and V_s), the arrival time of P- and S-waves were manually picked according to ASTM D5777
175 Standard [55].

176 **3.3. Testing Plan**

177 Multi-Stage Elastic (MSE) and cyclic tests were conducted in this study to characterize the non-
178 linear, pressure-dependent, and inelastic response of the Marcellus Shale specimens. P-wave
179 and cross-polarized S-wave velocities were measured at different points along the stress path to
180 (i) estimate dynamic moduli, and (ii) investigate the sensitivity of the velocity measurements to
181 changes in the micro-structure of the specimen due to variation in stress conditions. Details of the
182 stress path for MSE and cyclic tests are provided in the following sections.

183 **3.3.1. The Multi-Stage Elastic (MSE) Tests**

184 Due to rock specimen variability and scarcity, MSE test can be performed on a single specimen
185 to obtain the geo-mechanical parameters, instead of performing multiple single-stage triaxial tests
186 on multiple specimens [e.g. 11,19]. Several studies have shown that the results from a MSE test
187 on shale specimens [e.g. 11,56] or on Berea Sandstone specimens [e.g. 57] agree well with those
188 from single stage triaxial tests. Although the design of stress path is unique in each study, MSE
189 tests are usually performed at multiple stages, where each stage consists of applying a constant
190 CP, followed by few cycles of differential stress (loading/unloading) to fully characterize the
191 specimen's elastic properties, non-linearity, and plastic deformations at different stress levels.

192 Five different regions in stress-strain response of a rock specimen subjected to triaxial loading
193 can be observed [58,59] as depicted in Figure 3(a), including "(I) crack closure, (II) linear elastic
194 deformation, (III) crack initiation (CI) and stable crack growth, (IV) crack damage (CD) and
195 unstable crack growth, and (V) ultimate failure" [58,59]. In region I (low differential stress levels),
196 the behavior of the rock is usually nonlinear, in part, due to closure of micro-cracks [58,59]. In
197 region II, rock exhibits linear elastic response with the increase in differential stress. In region III,
198 crack initiation (CI), with stable cracks, due to damage of grain boundaries occurs. In region IV,
199 crack damage (CD) threshold and unstable crack growth occur [58,59]. In region V, the peak
200 (failure) strength is reached. While performing an MSE test, in order to stay within the elastic
201 range, usually the differential stress is kept below 50% of Unconfined Compressive Strength
202 (UCS) and 3 times of CP. This implies that only regions I and II are present in stress-strain
203 response in MSE tests.

204 Figure 3(b) shows the stress path followed during MSE tests, which consisted of seven stages.
205 For each stage of the test, CP was applied and held constant for 2 hours to ensure that the
206 compaction and equilibrium of the specimen were achieved (i.e. no further changes in axial and
207 radial strains). Then, one to two cycles of differential stress were applied as depicted in Figures

208 3(c)-(e). The loading/unloading rate for both CP and DS was set as 0.333 MPa/sec. At the
209 completion of each stage, CP was increased to the next level as shown in Figure 3(f). Throughout
210 the test, CP was increased step-wise in 5 MPa increments up to 50 MPa (the approximate in-situ
211 overburden stress for the tested shale specimens). The ultrasonic P- and S-wave velocities were
212 measured at different points along the stress path as shown in Figure 3(f) for Stage 3 of the test,
213 as an example. At each stage, the seismic velocities were measured (i) immediately after
214 application of CP, (ii) after achieving equilibrium (after 2 hours), and (iii) during application of
215 differential stress at different stress levels as shown in Figure 3(f). Figure 3(g) shows the labeling
216 of static measurements at each stage. In this study, static moduli (including Young's, and shear
217 moduli, and Poisson's ratio) were evaluated at different stress levels through MSE test.

218 **3.3.2. Cyclic Tests**

219 Cyclic tests are helpful in evaluating the gradual degradation, non-linear, and hysteresis behavior
220 of rocks. In cyclic tests, the CP is first increased to the desired level and kept constant during the
221 test. Then, the cycles of loading/unloading are performed, as shown in Figure 4(a). The lower and
222 upper bounds of differential stress can be prescribed, and a few cycles be performed to
223 investigate (i) the potential degradation in loading/unloading moduli, and (ii) plastic deformations.

224 First CP was increased step-wise in 5 MPa increments up to 30 MPa. In each step, CP was held
225 constant for 2 hours to ensure the compaction/equilibrium of the specimen was achieved (i.e. no
226 further changes in axial/radial strains). Then, differential stress ranging from 0 to 48 MPa was
227 applied as shown in Figure 4(b). When characterizing non-linear material (e.g. shale), it is
228 recommended to perform loading/unloading cycles at different stress levels to better characterize
229 the response of the specimen within the elastic range [33]. Within each cycle,
230 loading/unloading/reloading sub-cycles were performed at multiple stress levels as shown in
231 Figure 4(b). In addition, ultrasonic velocities were measured at different points along the stress
232 path as shown in Figures 4(b).

233 **3.4. Summary of Experiments**

234 Table 1 presents the details of the experimental conditions for the set of experiments reported in
235 this study. MSE tests were performed on R1 (calcite/quartz-rich) and R3 (clay-rich) specimens.
236 The cyclic type I test was performed on R2 (calcite/quartz-rich) and R4 (clay-rich) specimens. It
237 should be also noted that all the experiments were performed on dry specimens as (i) re-

238 saturation process could damage these specimens [11], and (ii) low permeability of the specimens
 239 necessitates long time (e.g. weeks to months) to perform drained test [e.g. 19].

240 3.5. Estimation of Static and Dynamic Moduli

241 The elastic properties of rocks can be estimated using either (i) strain measurements (static
 242 moduli), or (ii) ultrasonic wave velocities (dynamic moduli) [e.g. 33,60]. Vertical Transverse
 243 Isotropic (VTI) medium is referred to a condition where the characteristics of the material is
 244 symmetric about an axis normal to the plane of isotropy [e.g. 7,61]. Extracting a core from deep
 245 underground (a depth of about 2-3 km) leads to relief of in-situ stresses and subsequently creates
 246 some micro-cracks in the direction of bedding planes [25], resulting in higher degree of anisotropy
 247 when tested in the laboratory rather than in-situ testing of the rock mass. At macroscopic scale,
 248 shale rocks can be treated as VTI medium [11].

249 In a triaxial test, where axial and radial stresses and strains are measured, stress-strain
 250 relationship can be expressed as [11,61]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta\varepsilon_a \\ \delta\varepsilon_r \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_v & -2\nu_{vh}/E_v \\ -2\nu_{vh}/E_v & -(1-\nu_{hh})/E_h \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta\sigma_a \\ \delta\sigma_r \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

251 where ν_{vh} and E_v are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio in vertical direction, while, ν_{hh} and E_h
 252 are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio in horizontal direction; σ_a and σ_r are axial and radial
 253 stresses, respectively; and ε_a and ε_r are axial and radial strains, respectively. For a VTI medium,
 254 Eq. (1) reduces to [11,61]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta\varepsilon_v \\ \delta\varepsilon_s \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/K & -1/J \\ -1/J & 1/3G \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta p \\ \delta q \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

255 where K , J , and G are bulk, coupling, and shear moduli, respectively; ε_s is the distortional strain
 256 ($\varepsilon_s = \frac{2}{3}(\varepsilon_a - \varepsilon_r)$); ε_v is the volumetric strain ($\varepsilon_v = \varepsilon_a + 2\varepsilon_r$); q is the differential stress ($q = \sigma_1 -$
 257 σ_3); and p is the mean stress ($p = \frac{1}{3}(\sigma_1 + 2\sigma_3)$).

258 The coupling modulus (J) is defined when the rock is considered to obey the rules of VTI medium.
 259 For static measurements, bulk (K) modulus can be estimated based on the strain data during the

260 hydrostatic stage, while, Poisson's ratio (ν), and Young's (E) modulus can be estimated based on
261 the strain data during the triaxial stage of the experiment as shown in Figure 5.

262 K and J can be only estimated during hydrostatic stage of an experiment. In this study, K and J
263 were estimated from isotropic compression (hydrostatic) stage of cyclic tests for R2 and R4
264 specimens as illustrated in Figures 5(a) and 5(b). Young's and shear moduli, and Poisson's ratio
265 were estimated based on stress-strain curves during triaxial stage as illustrated in Figures 5(c)
266 and 5(d). Since, irreversible deformations occur for shale rocks, even at small differential stress
267 levels [33], we refer to the estimated moduli from stress-strain curves as static moduli rather than
268 elastic.

269 Using ultrasonic wave velocities, dynamic moduli can be estimated for an elastic, isotropic,
270 homogeneous, and solid material as [60]:

$$E = \frac{\rho V_S^2 (3V_P^2 - 4V_S^2)}{V_P^2 - V_S^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\nu = \frac{V_P^2 - 2V_S^2}{2(V_P^2 - V_S^2)} \quad (4)$$

$$G = \rho V_S^2 \quad (5)$$

271 where E , G and ν are, Young's, and shear moduli and Poisson's ratio, respectively; V_p and V_s are
272 P- and S-wave velocities, respectively; and ρ is the bulk density of the material [60]. Dynamic
273 moduli of the shale specimens at different stress levels along the stress path in MSE and cyclic
274 tests were estimated using the measured P- and S-wave (average of S_1 and S_2) velocities through
275 Eqs. (3) to (5).

276 4. RESULTS

277 The strain and P- and S-wave velocity measurements are provided for (i) MSE tests on R1 and
278 R3 specimens in Section 4.1, (ii) cyclic tests on R2 and R4 specimens in Section 4.2. More in-
279 depth discussions are provided in Section 5.

280 4.1. MSE Tests

281 Figure 6 shows the variation of axial and radial strains (average of the two pairs of strain gauges)
282 with differential stress at different levels of confining levels for the MSE test on R1 (calcite/quartz-
283 rich) specimen. As evident from Figure 6, at all stages of the test, the radial strains are much
284 lower than axials, an indication of volume loss, which is possibly accommodated by the closure
285 of microcracks and compaction of organic matter [7,11]. At very low confining levels (i.e. 0, 5, 10
286 MPa), the specimen exhibits substantial degree of non-linearity (axial stress-strain response) and
287 plastic deformations. In addition to the mineral elastic deformations that occur during loading,
288 frictional sliding and microcrack growth could induce energy-dissipative inelastic deformations
289 [14,62]. These plastic deformations can change the micro-structure of the rock specimen and
290 subsequently, affect the response of the rock specimen.

291 As expected, increasing the confinement level significantly affects the response of the specimen.
292 As it can be seen in Figure 6, at higher confining levels, the plastic deformations and the degree
293 of non-linearity of the specimen's response decrease. The plastic deformations at CP levels of
294 30, 40, and 50 MPa decrease significantly (close to zero) compared to those at lower CP levels,
295 which might be due to combination of high confining levels and successive loading. The estimated
296 static moduli at different confining levels for different loading/unloading conditions (as illustrated
297 in Figure 3(g)) are presented in Table 2. As expected, static measurements of Poisson's ratio,
298 Young's, and shear moduli increase with increase in confining level. For example, the Young's
299 modulus corresponding to first loading at CP=5, 20, and 50 MPa are estimated as 12, 23, and 29
300 GPa, respectively.

301 Figure 7 shows the variation of axial and radial strains with differential stress at different confining
302 levels for the MSE test on R3 (clay-rich) specimen. As evident in Figure 7, the radial strains are
303 lower than axials, and the plastic deformations and the non-linear behavior become less
304 pronounced at higher confinement levels, as was also observed for the R1 specimen. At low
305 differential stress levels (i.e. up to ~6 MPa), the specimen exhibits a significant degree of non-
306 linearity, which could be attributed to the closure/creation of existing/new micro-cracks. Similar to
307 R1 specimen, as evident in Table 2, static measurements of Poisson's ratio, Young's, and shear
308 moduli increase with increase in confining level. For example, the Young's modulus
309 corresponding to first loading at CP=5, 20, and 50 MPa are estimated as 7, 10, and 13 GPa,
310 respectively.

311 Figures 8(a) and 8(b) show the P- and S-wave velocity measurements super-imposed on the
312 stress path followed during MSE tests on R1 and R3 specimens, respectively. The magnitude of
313 P- and S-wave velocities for R1 specimen ranges from 1400 to 4800 and 1000 to 2950 m/s,
314 respectively. On the other hand, the magnitude of P- and S-wave velocities for R3 specimen
315 ranges from 1000 to 2600 and 1400 to 1900 m/s, respectively. The higher P- and S-wave velocity
316 measurements for R1 specimen compared to R3, given the same frequency of velocity
317 measurements constant at 750 kHz, could be attributed to the higher stiffness of this specimen
318 due to the fact that it is composed of stiffer minerals.

319 The estimated dynamic moduli at different confining levels for different loading/unloading
320 conditions are presented in Table 2. For example, the estimated dynamic Young's modulus for
321 R1 specimen at CP=5, 20, 50 MPa were estimated as 35, 42, 49 GPa, respectively, which are
322 192%, 83%, and 69% higher than static measurements, respectively. On the other hand, the
323 values of dynamic Young's moduli for R3 specimen at CP=5, 20, 50 MPa were estimated as
324 19,17, and 20 GPa, respectively, which are 171%, 70%, and 54% higher than static
325 measurements, respectively.

326 The P- and S-wave velocity measurements for both R1 and R3 specimens substantially increase
327 during Stage 1 (CP=0; Figure 3(c)) of the tests. In the subsequent stages, the S-wave velocity
328 measurements stay relatively constant, however, the P-wave velocity measurements follow the
329 loading/unloading trend of the stress path, that is lower velocities at lower differential stress levels
330 and higher velocities at higher levels. This indicates that the stress level (i.e. both confining and
331 differential) directly affects the ultrasonic velocities. Also, it can be observed from Figures 8(a)
332 and 8(b) that at higher confinement levels, the velocities are increasing, indicating the closure of
333 the existing micro-cracks.

334 **4.2. Cyclic Tests**

335 Figure 9(b) illustrates the time-history axial and radial strains for R2 (calcite/quartz-rich) specimen
336 subjected to cyclic test, with stress path as presented in Figure 9(a). Since the specimen was
337 axially loaded during triaxial stage, the axial strains were higher compared to radials as also
338 observed during MSE tests. The range of axial strain variation in the latter cycles of the test, under
339 the same upper and lower bound of differential stress, is smaller than those during earlier cycles
340 of the test. This could be an indication of slight hardening of the specimen. In addition,
341 transitioning from the first cycle to the second, there is an apparent plastic deformation (~0.3 milli-

342 strains), however, in the subsequent cycles, no obvious additional plastic deformations can be
343 observed. Therefore, the permanent plastic deformation at the end of the experiment appears to
344 be caused during the first cycle. Figure 9(c) shows the variation of axial, radial, and volumetric
345 strains against differential stress. Highly non-linear behavior and hysteresis are observed during
346 loading/unloading/reloading cycles, particularly during the first cycle.

347 The estimated static moduli at different loading/unloading/reloading conditions are presented in
348 Table 3. In general, the estimated static Young's modulus during (i) unloading is the highest, (ii)
349 loading is the lowest, and (iii) reloading is the intermediate. For example, the static Young's
350 modulus in the first cycle at DS of 30 MPa measured during loading, unloading, and reloading
351 stages are 23.3, 29.4, and 26.5 GPa, respectively. In the successive cycles, the static Young's
352 modulus is continuously increasing under the same stress conditions. For example, the reloading
353 Young's modulus at DS of 30 MPa measured during loading path for cycles 1 to 4 are 26.5, 31.4,
354 32.9, and 38.1 GPa, indicating 44% increase in the estimated Young's modulus.

355 Ultrasonic velocities were measured during all loading/unloading/reloading cycles of the test on
356 R2 specimen. For clarity, only measured velocities immediately after loading or immediately
357 before unloading (Figure 4(b)) are shown in Figure 9(d). The magnitude of P- and S-wave
358 velocities ranges from 4500 to 4800 and 2650 to 2950 m/s, respectively. Table 3, based on these
359 velocity measurements, presents the estimated dynamic moduli. In general, the dynamic Young's
360 modulus is not altering in sub-cycles of loading/unloading/reloading within a cycle. For example,
361 the estimated dynamic Young's modulus in the first cycle at DS of 30 MPa measured during
362 loading, unloading, and reloading stages are 50.1, 51.4, and 51.4 GPa, respectively. In the earlier
363 cycles, the dynamic Young's modulus increases following by a decrease in the latter cycles under
364 the same stress conditions. For example, the dynamic reloading Young's modulus at DS of 30
365 measured during loading stage for cycles 1 to 4 are 51.4, 52.1, 51.4, and 50.7 GPa.

366 The variations of both P- and S-wave velocities follow those of differential stress, which indicates
367 the sensitivity of measured velocities in response to the change in the internal structure of the
368 rock specimen (i.e. closure/opening of existing/new micro-cracks). For example, as indicated
369 from axial strain measurements in Figure 9(b), the permanent plastic deformation in the specimen
370 was caused during the first cycle. This is reflected in the increase of P-wave measurements at
371 the beginning of the second cycle, compared to that of the first cycle. As evident in Figure 9(d),
372 at a specific differential stress level, the measured velocities during the unloading part of each
373 cycle are slightly higher than those during the loading part. This could be in part due to the fact

374 that some of the closed micro-cracks during loading, do not open up after unloading, which in
375 turn, leads to the increased velocity measurements.

376 Figure 10(b) shows the time evolution of axial and radial strains for R4 specimen subjected to
377 cyclic test, with stress path presented in Figure 10(a). Although the followed stress path during
378 this experiment was very similar to that for specimen R2, the lower bound of the differential stress
379 in this test was prescribed as ~ 7 MPa. As it can be seen from Figure 10(b), the specimen exhibits
380 plastic deformations (total of ~ 0.7 milli-strains) distributed in successive loading cycles, as
381 opposed to the R2 specimen, which exhibited plastic deformation mostly in the first cycle (~ 0.3
382 milli-strains). In addition to the observed plastic deformations in the axial direction, plastic
383 deformations are observed in the radial direction in each cycle (total of ~ 0.8 milli-strains).

384 Figure 10(c) shows the variation of axial, radial, and volumetric strains against differential stress.
385 A non-linear response is observed at different stress levels within each cycle, particularly, the first
386 cycle. As successive cycles continue, the hysteresis in volumetric strains becomes more
387 pronounced, which can be attributed to the closure of the existing microcracks and compaction of
388 organic and clay content. The estimated static moduli at different loading/unloading/reloading
389 cycles are presented in Table 4. In general, the estimated static Young's modulus during 2nd
390 unloading in unloading part of a cycle is higher than static Young's modulus during loading in the
391 loading part of a cycle. For example, the Young's modulus in the first cycle during loading and 2nd
392 unloading stages at DS of 30 MPa are 14.8 and 16.9 GPa, respectively.

393 Figure 10(d) shows the measured P- and S-wave velocities during cyclic test on R4 specimen.
394 The magnitude of P- and S-wave velocities ranges from 2900 to 3200 and 1750 to 1900 m/s,
395 respectively. Similar to R2 specimen, the variations of both P- and S-wave velocities follow those
396 of differential stress, although, the magnitudes of velocities are less than those for R2 specimen,
397 due to the difference in the mineralogical composition. The estimated dynamic moduli, based on
398 these velocity measurements, are presented in Table 4, indicating that they are relatively constant
399 except those of the second cycle. For example, the average dynamic Young's modulus (for
400 loading/unloading/reloading) in cycles 1 to 4 during loading stage at DS of 30 MPa are 21.8, 22.2,
401 22.1, and 21.9 GPa, respectively.

402 Since the direction of axial loading in MSE and cyclic tests was perpendicular to the bedding
403 planes, compaction of bedding planes was expected to significantly contribute to the axial strain.
404 The difference between axial and radial strains during isotropic compression was used to

405 investigate the deformation anisotropy of the tested shale specimens. At the beginning of the
406 cyclic tests, the confining stress was increased from ~1 to ~30 MPa (rate: 0.333 MPa/sec). Figure
407 11(a) and 11(b) show the variation of $e_a - e_r$ against confining stress for the R2 (calcite/quartz-rich)
408 and R4 (clay-rich) specimens, respectively, during isotropic compression. As evident in Figure
409 11(a), R2 specimen exhibits some degree of anisotropy, with less pronounced anisotropy levels
410 at higher confining stresses. More significant anisotropy level can be observed for R4 specimen
411 (see Figure 11(b)) compared to R2 specimen, which can be in part attributed to the different
412 mineralogical content of these two specimens.

413 **5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION**

414 The shale rocks are typically highly-inhomogeneous and anisotropic which make them inelastic
415 material [e.g. 3, 14]. In addition, the tested rock specimens in this study had multiple micro-cracks,
416 resulted from stress relief during coring process, in the direction of the bedding planes (see Figure
417 2(f)), which cannot transfer the applied stress [33]. Therefore, the closure/opening of these micro-
418 cracks during loading/unloading leads to variation in elastic moduli. In addition, these
419 characteristics of shale rocks lead to pressure dependency and non-linear behavior, particularly
420 upon application of differential stress.

421 **5.1. Response of Specimen to Loading/Unloading/Reloading Cycles**

422 Both calcite/quartz- and clay-rich specimens show a nonlinear axial stress-strain response with a
423 higher non-linearity observed for the clay-rich specimens. This might be due to their higher clay
424 content compared to the calcite/quartz-rich specimens. At lower differential stress levels, a higher
425 degree of non-linearity is observed which could be attributed to the closure of the initial micro-
426 cracks at very low stress levels, with an accelerated pace. On the other hand, a significant amount
427 of non-linearity is observed for radial stress-strain for the clay-rich specimens under cyclic tests.

428 There is an increasing trend in the estimated static Young's modulus with differential stress for
429 both calcite/quartz- and clay-rich specimens. This can be attributed to the fact that within the
430 range of the applied differential stresses, the specimens are below the crack initiation threshold
431 (see Figure 3(a)), and therefore, new micro-cracks are not created, rather some of the existing
432 micro-cracks are being closed. As evident in Tables 3 and 4, the estimated static Young's modulus
433 is affected by the loading/unloading/reloading cycles. As also observed in other studies [e.g. 7, 11],
434 the estimated static Young's modulus is (i) the highest during unloading, (ii) the lowest during
435 loading, and (iii) the intermediate during reloading. For example, the estimated static Young's

436 modulus in unloading is 7% higher than that of loading. Although, this ratio is affected by the
437 confinement level and is reduced from 1.51 at CP=10 MPa to 1.04 at CP=50 MPa.

438 The observed difference between Young's modulus in loading and unloading could be, in part,
439 attributed to the fact that during loading both elastic and inelastic deformations occur, while during
440 unloading, elastic deformations are more dominant [7,11]. Therefore, the unloading Young's
441 modulus might be a better indication of the elastic properties of the rock specimens [11,60]. On
442 the other hand, the estimated dynamic Young's modulus is not affected by
443 loading/unloading/reloading cycles. This observation is in-line with the fact that dynamic
444 measurements do not capture plastic deformations of the rock specimen regardless of the type
445 of loading/unloading/reloading, rather indicate the elastic properties of the rock [33].

446 In all experiments, in general, the estimated static and dynamic Young's moduli at a specific stress
447 level during the unloading path are slightly higher compared to the loading path under the same
448 stress level. This can be an indication of the closure of some of the fractures upon loading and
449 not opening up after releasing the stress.

450 **5.2. Sensitivity of P- and S-wave Velocity to Variation in Stress Conditions**

451 Both P- and S-wave velocities are sensitive to changes in differential stress during loading and
452 unloading. At low stress levels, the existing micro-cracks (coring/stress-relieved) are closed
453 (region I in Figure 3(a)), and as DS increases (within region II), additional closure of
454 existing/inherent micro-cracks occurs. Upon unloading, some of the closed fractures open up
455 again. The closure/opening of these microfractures during loading/unloading affects the ultrasonic
456 velocities. At lower differential stresses, the relationship between velocity and applied stress is
457 almost linear [e.g. 40,63].

458 There are two sources of non-linearity as the shale specimen is loaded: (i) closure of micro-cracks,
459 and (ii) potential plastic response of solid matrix [11,40,63]. Other materials such as sandstone
460 can show a high degree of non-linearity between velocity and stress [64,65], which is usually
461 attributed to grain contact stiffening and micro-crack closure [40]. As obvious from SEM images
462 (see Figures 1(e) and 1(f)), the shales in this study have micro-cracks, and therefore, it is
463 hypothesized that the fractures in shales behave in a different way than those in sandstone. This
464 observation could be related to differences in shale matrix compressibility, shale fracture
465 compliance compared to sandstone [40].

466 At a particular DS level in successive cycles, the measured velocities continuously increase for
467 both calcite/quartz- and clay-rich specimens (see Figures 9(d) and 10(d)), except for the last cycle
468 of the clay-rich specimen. The increase of ultrasonic velocities in successive cycles could be due
469 to compaction of the specimen and permanent closure of some of the micro-cracks, while, the
470 decrease of the measured velocities transitioning from 3rd to 4th cycle in the clay-rich specimen
471 could be due to the fact that some new micro-cracks are created, which is the onset of crack
472 initiation (region III in Figure 3(a)).

473 By increasing the confining level, the ratio of V_p/V_s versus V_p continuously increases as shown in
474 Figure 12(a), indicating the effect of confinement on the velocity measurements. On the other
475 hand, as it can be seen from Figure 12(b), under constant confining level, the V_p/V_s ratio versus
476 V_p remains almost constant, indicating that increasing/decreasing differential stress does not
477 change V_p/V_s at a constant confining level, consistent with the observation in other studies [e.g.
478 39].

479 **5.3. Pressure-dependency of Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio**

480 The variation of estimated static and dynamic Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio with confining
481 level are illustrated in Figures 13(a) and 13(b) for R1 (calcite/quartz-rich) specimen, and in
482 Figures 13(c) and 13(d) for R3 (clay-rich) specimen, respectively. As expected and evident in
483 Figures 13(a)-(d), the estimated Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio from both static and dynamic
484 measurements increase with the increase in confining level. In general, the variation of both static
485 and dynamic Young's modulus follow a linear trend with relatively good regression values, except
486 that of estimated dynamic Young's modulus for R4 specimen. It should be noted that two different
487 trends are identifiable for CP levels below and above 30 MPa, indicating that the closure of micro-
488 cracks becomes less dominant as higher levels of CP are applied. This could be explained by the
489 smaller number of open micro-cracks at higher confinement levels compared to those at lower
490 confinement levels. Therefore, there is less room for further changes in Young's modulus at higher
491 confinement levels. Estimations of static and dynamic Poisson's ratio, on the other hand, show a
492 nonlinear relationship with confining level. At close-to-zero confining level, the very low Poisson's
493 ratio estimations are attributed to the initial closure of horizontal cracks, which leads to high axial
494 strain compared to radial strain, as also observed by Villamor Lora et al. [11].

495 The combined effect of CP and DS on the estimated static and dynamic Young's modulus for R1
496 and R3 specimens are shown in Figures 13(e) and 13(f), respectively, where the variation of P-

497 and S-wave velocities with mean stress are illustrated. It can be observed that at a constant CP,
498 as higher differential stress is applied (i.e. higher mean stress at a constant CP), the estimated
499 dynamic Young's modulus for both specimens and static Young's modulus for the calcite/quartz-
500 rich specimen increases, while, the estimated static Young's modulus for clay-rich specimen
501 decreases. This difference in response of calcite/quartz- and clay-rich specimens could be
502 attributed to the difference in mineralogy composition.

503 **5.4. Comparison of Static and Dynamic Moduli Estimation**

504 In general, the estimated dynamic moduli are higher than those of static [11,33,66]. This
505 difference can be attributed to: (i) the significantly higher strain amplitudes for static
506 measurements compared to dynamic measurements, (ii) stress concentration at grain contact
507 and consequently exceeding the elastic limit of the minerals, and (iii) stress-induced changes in
508 porosity [33]. For shale rocks, plasticity and non-linearity effects as well as the heterogeneous
509 micro-structure can further contribute to this difference between static and dynamic moduli [33].

510 As evident in Figure 13, the dynamic moduli are higher than static. It should be noted that at low
511 confinement levels, the relationship between the static and dynamic moduli is not reliable,
512 however, as the confinement level increases the difference becomes smaller. This observation,
513 in part, can be explained by the fact that the microcracks affect the strain data more than velocities
514 [66]. Strain amplitude and subsequently the static moduli estimated from unloading/reloading
515 cycles are intermediate between static moduli estimated during loading and dynamic moduli
516 (either loading/unloading/reloading).

517 The ratio of Young's modulus estimated based on velocity measurements to that estimated based
518 on strain measurements, i.e. $\frac{E_{dynamic}}{E_{static}}$, can be affected by clay and organic content of the
519 specimen. The average $\frac{E_{dynamic}}{E_{static}}$ is about 1.7 and 1.4 for calcite/quartz-rich and clay-rich
520 specimens, respectively.

521 **5.5. Hysteresis Effects**

522 The evolution of plastic deformation with CP and DS levels for both calcite/quartz-rich and clay-
523 rich specimens is presented in Table 5 implying that under the same level of differential stress,
524 the plastic deformations decrease as confinement level increases. In addition, it is worth noting
525 that at CP=0 MPa, the applied differential stress is around 5 MPa, leading to relatively small plastic

526 deformation. Furthermore, at a specific confinement level, the plastic deformations increase with
527 increase in differential stress. The clay-rich specimen follows a trend similar to that observed for
528 calcite/quartz specimen, with few discrepancies. In addition, As it can be found from Figures 9(d)
529 and 10(d), during cyclic loading, the S-wave velocities do not show hysteresis effects, while the
530 P-wave velocities show some degree of hysteresis, similar observation to Jones and Wang [41]
531 for dry shale rocks.

532 **6. CONCLUSIONS**

533 The design of an optimized hydraulic fracturing programme and the development of production
534 models require the laboratory characterization of shale gas formations. In this study, Marcellus
535 Shale rock core plugs, retrieved from a deep well in West Virginia at a depth of ~2270 m, were
536 characterized through a series of triaxial tests with concurrent measurements of ultrasonic P- and
537 S-wave velocities at different stress conditions. Based on the mineralogy, the specimens were
538 categorized into calcite/quartz-rich and clay-rich. It was found that the planes of weakness and
539 the existing microcracks (residing in clay content and sub-parallel to the bedding planes) play a
540 major role in response of these rocks.

541 For characterization of elastic, hysteresis, and plastic properties of the specimens tested in this
542 study, a series of multi-stage elastic and cyclic test, supplemented by velocity measurements,
543 were performed. It was found that both type of specimens show a substantially nonlinear
544 response, with higher degree of nonlinearity for clay-rich specimens. The nonlinear response was
545 more pronounced at low differential stress levels, where the closure of microcracks might occur.
546 The ultrasonic P- and S-wave velocities were found to be sensitive to changes in the internal
547 structure of the rock caused by variation in stress conditions. The changes in measured velocities
548 were more significant during isotropic compression stages of the tests, where confining level was
549 increased, compared to triaxial stages of the tests. Both static and dynamic estimations of
550 Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio increased with increase in confining level. At higher stress
551 levels, both estimated static and dynamic moduli increased, an indication that the compaction of
552 the specimens has occurred.

553 The estimated dynamic Young's modulus was found to be affected by the very small strain
554 amplitudes, and therefore, significantly higher than the static estimations at corresponding stress
555 level. The ratio of the estimated dynamic Young's modulus to static can be considered as a proxy
556 of the clay and organic content of the specimen. Therefore, the specimens with higher clay content

557 showed a lower ratio of dynamic to static Young's modulus, compared to that of calcite/quartz-
558 rich specimens. However, the static reloading/unloading Young's modulus in sub-cycles of the
559 cyclic tests were found to be the intermediate value between dynamic and static (during loading).
560 The slightly higher Young's modulus during unloading path was attributed to the fact that some of
561 the closed microcracks upon loading, were not opened up again after unloading, and
562 subsequently, the plastic deformations were not as substantial as those during loading path. It
563 was found that as the confining level increases, the plastic deformations become less significant,
564 while, increasing the differential stress on the specimens caused more significant plastic
565 deformations.

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Table 1. The information about shale specimens

Specimen	Specimen dimensions		Depth (ft)	Mineralogical Content (wt. %)						Performed Test	CP* ³ (MPa)	DS* ⁴ (MPa)	
	D* ¹ (mm)	L* ² (mm)		Calcite	Dolomite	Gypsum	Illite	Muscovite	Pyrite				Quartz
R1	38.04	56.87	7486	38.5	5.2	-	-	30.2	-	26.1	MSE* ⁵	0 to 30	0 to 30
R2	38.07	65.26									Cyclic	30	0 to 45
R3	38.03	60.34									MSE	0 to 50	0 to 30
R4	38.05	65.42	7467	2.9	-	4.1	69	-	3.1	20.8	Cyclic	30	0 to 45

*¹D: Diameter of the Specimen
 *²L: Length of the Specimen
 *³CP: Confining Pressure
 *⁴DS: Differential Stress
 *⁵MSE: Multi-Stage Elastic

740 **Table 2.** Estimated static/dynamic moduli from MSE test for the R1 and R3 specimens

Specimen	CP (MPa)	DS (MPa)	Type	E (GPa)	v (%)	G (GPa)
R1 (Calcite/quartz-rich)	0	0-15-0	Static	9.1L ^{1st} -11.1U ^{1st}	6.0L ^{1st} -6.7U ^{1st}	4.0L ^{1st} -4.8U ^{1st}
		15	Dynamic	33.9	114.9	7.9
	5	0-15-0	Static	11.5L ^{1st} -17.4U ^{1st}	9.3L ^{1st} -11.3U ^{1st}	4.8L ^{1st} -6.9U ^{1st}
		15	Dynamic	35.1	13.6	15.5
	10	0-15-0-30-0	Static	18.2L ^{1st} -20.7U ^{1st} - 17.9R ^{2nd} -22.4U ^{2nd}	11.0L ^{1st} -13.1U ^{1st} - 11.9R ^{2nd} -14.4U ^{2nd}	7.2L ^{1st} -7.9U ^{1st} - 7.0R ^{2nd} -8.4U ^{2nd}
		15,30	Dynamic	37.8,41.8	17.3,20.7	16.1,17.3
	20	0-15-0-30-0	Static	22.8L ^{1st} -25.0U ^{1st} - 23.8R ^{2nd} -25.8U ^{2nd}	15.4L ^{1st} -16.5U ^{1st} - 16.0R ^{2nd} -17.9U ^{2nd}	8.4L ^{1st} -9.1U ^{1st} - 8.7R ^{2nd} -9.2U ^{2nd}
		15,30	Dynamic	41.8,44.9	19.0,18.7	17.6,18.9
	30	0-15-0-30-0	Static	28.6L ^{1st} -29.8U ^{1st} - 29.4R ^{2nd} -30.0U ^{2nd}	20.8L ^{1st} -21.4U ^{1st} - 21.7R ^{2nd} -22.0U ^{2nd}	9.9L ^{1st} -10.2U ^{1st} - 10.0R ^{2nd} -10.0U ^{2nd}
		15,30	Dynamic	47.5,48.5	23.0,24.7	19.3,19.5
	40	0-15-0-30-0	Static	30.0L ^{1st} -30.6U ^{1st} - 30.4R ^{2nd} -31.0U ^{2nd}	22.5L ^{1st} -23.2U ^{1st} - 23.6R ^{2nd} -24.0U ^{2nd}	N/A
		15,30	Dynamic	48.6,48.6	23.1,23.1	19.8,19.8
	50	0-15-0-30-0	Static	29.2L ^{1st} -30.4U ^{1st} - 30.0R ^{2nd} -31.0U ^{2nd}	23.3L ^{1st} -23.6U ^{1st} - 24.6R ^{2nd} -25.0U ^{2nd}	N/A
		15,30	Dynamic	48.8,49.7	24.4,23.2	19.6,20.2
R3 (Clay-rich)	0	0-15-0	Static	6.4L ^{1st} -6.7U ^{1st}	11.6L ^{1st} -10.9U ^{1st}	2.8L ^{1st} -2.9U ^{1st}
		15	Dynamic	4.9	-59.7	6.1
	5	0-15-0	Static	7.3L ^{1st} -8.8U ^{1st}	9.5L ^{1st} -11.0U ^{1st}	3.2L ^{1st} -3.8U ^{1st}
		15	Dynamic	18.6	13	8.2
	10	0-15-0-30-0	Static	8.8L ^{1st} -9.6U ^{1st} - 8.6R ^{2nd} -9.6U ^{2nd}	10.4L ^{1st} -11.8U ^{1st} - 13.5R ^{2nd} -14.7U ^{2nd}	3.8L ^{1st} -4.1U ^{1st} - 3.6R ^{2nd} -4.0U ^{2nd}
		15,30	Dynamic	14.8,16.7	(-12.2),(-6.2)	8.4,8.9
	20	0-15-0-30-0	Static	10.0L ^{1st} -10.9U ^{1st} - 9.8R ^{2nd} -10.7U ^{2nd}	11.6L ^{1st} -13.3U ^{1st} - 14.4R ^{2nd} -15.6U ^{2nd}	4.3L ^{1st} -4.6U ^{1st} - 4.1R ^{2nd} -4.4U ^{2nd}
		15,30	Dynamic	16.5,17.8	(-6.1),1.8	8.8,8.8
	30	0-15-0-30-0	Static	11.5L ^{1st} -12.0U ^{1st} - 11.0R ^{2nd} -11.5U ^{2nd}	12.7L ^{1st} -14.2U ^{1st} - 15.7R ^{2nd} -16.6U ^{2nd}	4.8L ^{1st} -5.0U ^{1st} - 4.5R ^{2nd} -4.7U ^{2nd}
		15,30	Dynamic	18,18.7	2.8,7.5	8.8,8.7
	40	0-15-0-30-0	Static	12.4L ^{1st} -12.6U ^{1st} - 11.8R ^{2nd} -12.2U ^{2nd}	13.0L ^{1st} -15.0U ^{1st} - 16.2R ^{2nd} -17.3U ^{2nd}	N/A
		15,30	Dynamic	18.9,19.4	3.3,8.8	9.1,8.9
	50	0-15-0-30-0	Static	13.1L ^{1st} -13.2U ^{1st} - 13.2R ^{2nd} -13.1U ^{2nd}	13.7L ^{1st} -15.6U ^{1st} - 17.7R ^{2nd} -18.4U ^{2nd}	N/A
		15,30	Dynamic	19.5,19.9	7.9,10	9.0,9.1

L^{1st}: first loading modulus; U^{1st}: first unloading modulus; R^{2nd}: reloading modulus; U^{2nd}: second unloading modulus

741 **Table 3.** Estimated dynamic and static moduli for R2 (calcite/quartz-rich) specimen under cyclic
 742 test (confining level is constant at 30 MPa)

Cycle	Moduli	Type	Differential Stress (MPa)							
			5		15		30		45	
			Loading	Unloading	Loading	Unloading	Loading	Unloading	Loading	Unloading
1	E (GPa)	Static	25.8L- 28.6U- 27.8R	22.4U ^{1st} - 28.6L- 28.1U ^{2nd}	27.1L- 28.6U- 31.5R	24.0U ^{1st} - 30.6L- 28.5U ^{2nd}	23.3L- 29.4U- 26.5R	27.4U ^{1st} - 30.3L- 27.4U ^{2nd}	13.7L- 41.5U- 29.3R	41.5U ^{1st} - 29.3L- 35.1U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	45.6L- 45.7U- 45.6R	47.0U ^{1st} - 46.7L- 46.8U ^{2nd}	48.3L- 48.4U- 48.5R	48.9U ^{1st} - 48.9L- 48.8U ^{2nd}	50.1L- 51.4U- 51.4R	52.0U ^{1st} - 52.1L- 52.1U ^{2nd}	50.9L- 52.9U- 53.0R	50.9L- 52.9U- 53.0R
	ν (%)	Static	22.6L- 21.9U- 21.0R	27.0U ^{1st} - 21.6L- 22.8U ^{2nd}	24.8L- 21.3U- 25.3R	29.5U ^{1st} - 23.8L- 23.7U ^{2nd}	34.7L- 32.0U- 23.2U	26.1U ^{1st} - 22.6L- 25.4U ^{2nd}	0L- 37.7U- 26.1R	37.7U ^{1st} - 26.1L- 24.5U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	22.6L- 23.0U- 23.0R	22.2U ^{1st} - 22.7L- 22.7U ^{2nd}	21.4L- 21.5U- 21.4R	21.9U ^{1st} - 21.9L- 22.0U ^{2nd}	20.7L- 19.6U- 19.4R	19.4U ^{1st} - 19.5L- 19.5U ^{2nd}	22.0L- 19.1U- 19.8R	22.0L- 19.1U- 19.8R
	G (GPa)	Static	9.8L- 10.9U- 10.7R	8.3U ^{1st} - 10.9L- 10.6U ^{2nd}	10.1L- 10.9U- 11.6R	8.7U ^{1st} - 11.4L- 10.7U ^{2nd}	8.2L- 10.3U- 10.0R	10.1U ^{1st} - 11.4L- 11.2U ^{2nd}	6.5L- 13.7U- 10.8R	13.7U ^{1st} - 10.8L- 12.8U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	18.6L- 18.6U- 18.6R	19.2U ^{1st} - 19.0L- 19.0U ^{2nd}	19.9L- 19.9U- 20.0R	20.1U ^{1st} - 20.1L- 20.0U ^{2nd}	20.7L- 21.5U- 21.5R	21.8U ^{1st} - 21.8L- 21.8U ^{2nd}	20.8L- 22.2U- 22.1R	20.8L- 22.2U- 22.1R
2	E (GPa)	Static	27.3L- 26.1U- 28.2R	23.6U ^{1st} - XXL- XXU ^{2nd}	27.7L- 30.7U- 29.4R	19.0U ^{1st} - 31.7L- 29.4U ^{2nd}	27.6L- 33.4U- 31.4R	25.6U ^{1st} - 29.3L- 31.3U ^{2nd}	37.9L- 35.2U- 31.2R	35.2U ^{1st} - 31.2L- 35.7U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	46.4L- 46.6U- 46.3R	47.3U ^{1st} - 46.6L- 46.9U ^{2nd}	48.7L- 49.0U- 48.7R	49.5U ^{1st} - 49.2L- 49.1U ^{2nd}	51.7L- 51.6U- 52.1R	52.3U ^{1st} - 52.0L- 52.4U ^{2nd}	52.8L- 53.4U- 53.4R	52.8L- 53.4U- 53.4R
	ν (%)	Static	17.5L- 19.8U- 19.6R	22.7U ^{1st} - XXL- XXU ^{2nd}	23.5L- 24.8U- 18.2R	25.6U ^{1st} - 25.2L- 23.9U ^{2nd}	25.9L- 24.5U- 22.2R	23.8U ^{1st} - 22.5L- 22.0U ^{2nd}	37.6L- 32.0U- 27.8R	32.0U ^{1st} - 27.8L- 22.2U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	22.9L- 23.3U- 23.1R	22.5U ^{1st} - 23.0L- 22.7U ^{2nd}	22.0L- 21.7U- 22.2R	21.4U ^{1st} - 21.8L- 22.1U ^{2nd}	19.5L- 20.0U- 19.6R	19.6U ^{1st} - 19.4L- 19.7U ^{2nd}	19.6L- 19.6U- 19.3R	19.6L- 19.6U- 19.3R
	G (GPa)	Static	10.8L- 10.1U- 10.9R	9.0U ^{1st} - XXL- XXU ^{2nd}	10.4L- 11.3U- 11.5R	7.2U ^{1st} - 11.6L- 11.0U ^{2nd}	10.2L- 12.3U- 11.8R	9.7U ^{1st} - 11.0L- 11.8U ^{2nd}	12.8L- 12.2U- 11.3R	12.2U ^{1st} - 11.3L- 13.3U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	18.9L- 18.9U- 18.8R	19.3U ^{1st} - 18.9L- 19.1U ^{2nd}	20.0L- 20.1U- 19.9R	20.4U ^{1st} - 20.2L- 20.1U ^{2nd}	21.6L- 21.5U- 21.8R	21.9U ^{1st} - 21.8L- 21.9U ^{2nd}	22.1L- 22.3U- 22.4R	22.1L- 22.3U- 22.4R
3	E (GPa)	Static	26.2L- 27.5U- 26.2R	17.9U ^{1st} - 31.1L- 26.4U ^{2nd}	28.1L- 31.2U- 29.9R	25.6U ^{1st} - 30.3L- 30.7U ^{2nd}	25.7L- 33.1U- 32.9R	26.8U ^{1st} - 30.7L- 30.9U ^{2nd}	28.2L- 31.9U- 34.9R	31.9U ^{1st} - 34.9L- 35.9U ^{2nd}

	v (%)	Dynamic	46.6L- 46.7U- 46.6R	47.2U ^{1st} - 47.1L- 46.9U ^{2nd}	48.5L- 48.7U- 48.8R	49.2U ^{1st} - 49.4L- 49.3U ^{2nd}	50.1L- 50.1U- 51.4R	52.0U ^{1st} - 52.1L- 52.3U ^{2nd}	53.2L- 53.2U- 52.9R	53.2L- 53.2U- 52.9R
		Static	20.9L- 21.9U- 18.9R	25.7U ^{1st} - 23.7L- 21.2U ^{2nd}	26.3L- 19.1U- 22.8R	22.7U ^{1st} - 25.4L- 23.2U ^{2nd}	23.8L- 20.3U- 23.0R	23.1U ^{1st} - 19.5L- 25.2U ^{2nd}	28.1L- 25.2U- 24.1R	25.2U ^{1st} - 24.1L- 27.5U ^{2nd}
	G (GPa)	Dynamic	23.2L- 22.9U- 22.8R	22.6U ^{1st} - 22.8L- 22.8U ^{2nd}	22.6L- 22.4U- 21.9R	21.8U ^{1st} - 21.7L- 22.1U ^{2nd}	22.0L- 22.1U- 20.2R	19.8U ^{1st} - 19.9L- 19.6U ^{2nd}	19.5L- 19.5U- 19.8R	19.5L- 19.5U- 19.8R
		Static	10.1L- 10.5U- 10.3R	6.8U ^{1st} - 11.6L- 10.2U ^{2nd}	10.3L- 12.0U- 11.2R	9.7U ^{1st} - 11.2L- 11.5U ^{2nd}	9.7L- 12.6U- 12.2R	10.1U ^{1st} - 11.8L- 11.4U ^{2nd}	10.2L- 11.7U- 12.8R	11.7U ^{1st} - 12.8L- 12.9U ^{2nd}
	G (GPa)	Dynamic	18.9L- 19.0U- 19.0R	19.2U ^{1st} - 19.2L- 19.1U ^{2nd}	19.8L- 19.9U- 20.0R	20.2U ^{1st} - 20.3L- 20.2U ^{2nd}	20.5L- 20.5U- 21.4R	21.7U ^{1st} - 21.7L- 21.9U ^{2nd}	22.3L- 22.3U- 22.1R	22.3L- 22.3U- 22.1R
		Static	28.7L- 32.0U- 25.9R	25.8U ^{1st} - 30.5L- 28.5U ^{2nd}	30.4L- 35.3U- 34.9R	27.4U ^{1st} - 34.6L- 28.4U ^{2nd}	27.6L- 30.3U- 38.1R	31.5U ^{1st} - 37.3L- 35.0U ^{2nd}	29.9L- 38.2U- 27.8R	38.2U ^{1st} - 27.8L- 27.9U ^{2nd}
4	E (GPa)	Dynamic	46.6L- 46.8U- 46.7R	47.2U ^{1st} - 46.7L- 46.8U ^{2nd}	48.7L- 48.8U- 48.8R	49.2U ^{1st} - 49.2L- 49.3U ^{2nd}	50.3L- 50.6U- 50.7R	52.5U ^{1st} - 52.3L- 50.6U ^{2nd}	51.5L- 51.5U- 53.5R	51.5L- 51.5U- 53.5R
		Static	22.4L- 22.7U- 21.7R	24.0U ^{1st} - 25.3L- 21.9U ^{2nd}	23.5L- 24.1U- 22.9R	22.3U ^{1st} - 27.3L- 21.4U ^{2nd}	24.1L- 20.9U- 22.3R	26.4U ^{1st} - 21.6L- 27.4U ^{2nd}	28.4L- 30.3U- 22.3R	30.3U ^{1st} - 22.3L- 24.0U ^{2nd}
	v (%)	Dynamic	23.0L- 22.9U- 23.1R	22.8U ^{1st} - 23.3L- 23.0U ^{2nd}	22.3L- 22.1U- 22.1R	22.1U ^{1st} - 22.6L- 22.2U ^{2nd}	21.8L- 22.4U- 21.8R	19.9U ^{1st} - 19.9L- 21.9U ^{2nd}	21.9L- 21.8U- 18.2R	21.9L- 21.8U- 18.2R
		Static	10.9L- 12.0U- 10.0R	9.7U ^{1st} - 11.2L- 10.9U ^{2nd}	11.4L- 13.0U- 13.0R	10.4U ^{1st} - 12.5L- 10.8U ^{2nd}	10.3L- 11.6U- 14.1R	11.5U ^{1st} - 13.9L- 12.5U ^{2nd}	10.8L- 13.4U- 10.7R	13.4U ^{1st} - 10.7L- 10.4U ^{2nd}
	G (GPa)	Dynamic	19.0L- 19.0U- 19.0R	19.2U ^{1st} - 18.9L- 19.0U ^{2nd}	19.9L- 20.0U- 20.0R	20.1U ^{1st} - 20.1L- 20.2U ^{2nd}	20.6L- 20.7U- 20.8R	21.9U ^{1st} - 21.8L- 20.8U ^{2nd}	21.1L- 21.1U- 22.6R	21.1L- 21.1U- 22.6R
		Static	10.9L- 12.0U- 10.0R	9.7U ^{1st} - 11.2L- 10.9U ^{2nd}	11.4L- 13.0U- 13.0R	10.4U ^{1st} - 12.5L- 10.8U ^{2nd}	10.3L- 11.6U- 14.1R	11.5U ^{1st} - 13.9L- 12.5U ^{2nd}	10.8L- 13.4U- 10.7R	13.4U ^{1st} - 10.7L- 10.4U ^{2nd}

L: first loading modulus; U: first unloading modulus; R^{2nd}: reloading modulus; 743
U^{1st}: first unloading modulus; L: second loading modulus; U^{2nd}: second unloading modulus

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748 **Table 4.** Estimated dynamic and static moduli for R4 specimen clay-rich specimen under cyclic
 749 test (confining level is constant at 30 MPa)

Cycle	Moduli	Type	Differential Stress (MPa)					
			15		30		45	
			Loading	Unloading	Loading	Unloading	Loading	Unloading
1	E (GPa)	Static	15.1L- 15.9U- 15.7R	16.1U ^{1st} - 15.4L- 15.3U ^{2nd}	14.8L- 16.8U- 16.0R	17.7U ^{1st} - 16.3L- 16.9U ^{2nd}	17.6L- 16.7U- 17.1R	16.7U ^{1st} - 17.1L- 16.3U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	20.9L- 21.0U- 21.0R	21.6U ^{1st} - 21.7L- 21.7U ^{2nd}	21.8L- 21.8U- 21.9R	22.1U ^{1st} - 22L- 22.2U ^{2nd}	22.3L- 22.4U- 22.4R	22.3U ^{1st} - 22.4L- 22.4U ^{2nd}
	ν (%)	Static	24.3L- 17.6U- 18.7R	34.0U ^{1st} - 18.0L- 19.2U ^{2nd}	31.3L- 18.1U- 20.2R	29.1U ^{1st} - 18.1L- 19.6U ^{2nd}	47.9L- 15.8U- 21.0R	15.8U ^{1st} - 21.0L- 17.9U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	20.8L- 20.6U- 21.3R	21.4U ^{1st} - 21.3L- 21.0U ^{2nd}	21.9L- 21.6U- 21.9R	21.3U ^{1st} - 21.7L- 21.7U ^{2nd}	21.9L- 22.3U- 22.4R	21.9U ^{1st} - 22.3L- 22.4U ^{2nd}
	G (GPa)	Static	5.7L- 6.3U- 6.2R	5.6U ^{1st} - 6.1L- 6.0U ^{2nd}	5.3L- 6.6U- 6.2R	6.4U ^{1st} - 6.4L- 6.6U ^{2nd}	5.6L- 6.7U- 6.6R	6.7U ^{1st} - 6.6L- 6.4U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	8.6L- 8.7U- 8.7R	8.9U ^{1st} - 8.9L- 9.0U ^{2nd}	9.0L- 9.0U- 9.0R	9.1U ^{1st} - 9.1L- 9.1U ^{2nd}	9.1L- 9.2U- 9.2R	9.1U ^{1st} - 9.2L- 9.2U ^{2nd}
2	E (GPa)	Static	16.6L- 16.5U- 16.6R	16.5U ^{1st} - 15.4L- 15.3U ^{2nd}	16.3L- 17.3U- 16.5R	17.7U ^{1st} - 16.6L- 16.7U ^{2nd}	15.6L- 16.8U- 16.7R	16.8U ^{1st} - 16.7L- 16.6U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	21.9L- 21.6U- 21.6R	21.7U ^{1st} - 21.7L- 21.8U ^{2nd}	22.1L- 22.2U- 22.2R	22.3U ^{1st} - 22.1L- 22.2U ^{2nd}	22.4L- 22.8U- 22.6R	22.4U ^{1st} - 22.8L- 22.6U ^{2nd}
	ν (%)	Static	27.9L- 18.7U- 20.6R	34.2U ^{1st} - 18.3L- 19.3U ^{2nd}	34.5L- 18.7U- 21.3R	30.5U ^{1st} - 20.0L- 20.0U ^{2nd}	37.3L- 17.6U- 21.0R	17.6U ^{1st} - 21.0L- 19.1U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	21.2L- 21.5U- 21.9R	21.3U ^{1st} - 21.9L- 20.9U ^{2nd}	21.9L- 21.6U- 22.5R	21.9U ^{1st} - 21.5L- 21.7U ^{2nd}	22.5L- 23.5U- 22.6R	22.5U ^{1st} - 23.5L- 22.6U ^{2nd}
	G (GPa)	Static	6.0L- 6.5U- 6.4R	5.7U ^{1st} - 6.1L- 6.0U ^{2nd}	5.7L- 6.7U-6.3	6.3U ^{1st} - 6.4L- 6.5U ^{2nd}	5.3L- 6.6U- 6.4R	6.6U ^{1st} - 6.4L- 6.5U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	9.1L- 8.9U- 8.9R	8.9U ^{1st} - 9.0L- 8.9U ^{2nd}	9.1L- 9.1U- 9.1R	9.1U ^{1st} - 9.1L- 9.1U ^{2nd}	9.1L- 9.2U- 9.2R	9.1U ^{1st} - 9.2L- 9.2U ^{2nd}

3	E (GPa)	Static	17.2L- 16.2U- 19.1R	17.0U ^{1st} - 15.5L- 15.6U ^{2nd}	16.7L- 17.3U- 17.0R	18.0U ^{1st} - 16.6L- 16.8U ^{2nd}	15.9L- 17.0U- 17.1R	17.0U ^{1st} - 17.1L- 16.3U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	21.7L- 21.7U- 21.7R	21.5U ^{1st} - 21.7L- 21.6U ^{2nd}	22.1L- 22.2U- 22.1R	22.3U ^{1st} - 22.0L- 22.1U ^{2nd}	22.5L- 22.3U- 22.5R	22.5U ^{1st} - 22.3L- 22.5U ^{2nd}
	ν (%)	Static	28.5L- 18.7U- 18.9R	34.8U ^{1st} - 18.5L- 19.0U ^{2nd}	36.0L- 18.5U- 21.0R	29.4U ^{1st} - 19.4L- 19.7U ^{2nd}	36.3L- 18.3U- 20.8R	18.3U ^{1st} - 20.8L- 18.0U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	21.2L- 21.3U- 21.9R	21.5U ^{1st} - 20.0L- 19.2U ^{2nd}	21.3L- 21.9U- 22.1R	20.5U ^{1st} - 20.8L- 19.9U ^{2nd}	22.1L- 21.2U- 22.2R	22.1U ^{1st} - 21.2L- 22.2U ^{2nd}
	G (GPa)	Static	6.2L- 6.4U- 7.4R	5.9U ^{1st} - 6.1L- 6.1U ^{2nd}	5.8L- 6.8U- 6.5R	6.5U ^{1st} - 6.5L- 6.5U ^{2nd}	5.5L- 6.7U- 6.6R	6.7U ^{1st} - 6.6L- 6.4U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	8.9L- 8.9U- 8.9R	9.0U ^{1st} - 8.9L- 9.0U ^{2nd}	9.1L- 9.1U- 9.1R	9.1U ^{1st} - 9.1L- 9.1U ^{2nd}	9.2L- 9.2U- 9.2R	9.2U ^{1st} - 9.2L- 9.2U ^{2nd}
4	E (GPa)	Static	17.6L- 16.1U- 16.7R	17.3U ^{1st} - 15.7L- 15.5U ^{2nd}	16.9L- 17.4U- 17.2R	18.1U ^{1st} - 16.7L- 17.4U ^{2nd}	16.5L- 17.0U- 16.6R	17.0U ^{1st} - 16.6L- 16.4U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	21.3L- 21.6U- 21.5R	21.4U ^{1st} - 21.5L- 21.6U ^{2nd}	21.8L- 21.9U- 22.0R	22.0U ^{1st} - 22.1L- 22.1U ^{2nd}	22.3L- 22.4U- 22.4R	22.3U ^{1st} - 22.4L- 22.4U ^{2nd}
	ν (%)	Static	29.1L- 18.4U- 20.9R	36.7U ^{1st} - 18.4L- 19.8U ^{2nd}	34.6L- 19.8U- 21.9R	30.0U ^{1st} - 19.7L- 20.5U ^{2nd}	37.6L- 19.0U- 20.6R	19.0L- 20.6L- 18.7U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	19.5L- 20.3U- 20.9R	19.3U ^{1st} - 19.9L- 19.9U ^{2nd}	20.5L- 20.3U- 20.9R	21.2U ^{1st} - 20.7L- 19.8U ^{2nd}	20.9L- 21.2U- 21.1R	20.9U ^{1st} - 21.2L- 21.1U ^{2nd}
	G (GPa)	Static	6.4L- 6.3U- 6.4R	5.9U ^{1st} - 6.2L- 6.0U ^{2nd}	5.9L- 6.7U- 6.5R	6.5U ^{1st} - 6.5L- 6.7U ^{2nd}	5.6L- 6.6U- 6.4R	6.6U ^{1st} - 6.4L- 6.4U ^{2nd}
		Dynamic	9.0L- 9.0U- 8.9R	8.9U ^{1st} - 9.0L- 9.0U ^{2nd}	9.0L- 9.1U- 9.1R	9.1U ^{1st} - 9.1L- 9.1U ^{2nd}	9.2L- 9.2U- 9.2R	9.2U ^{1st} - 9.2L- 9.2U ^{2nd}

L: first loading modulus; U: first unloading modulus; R^{2nd}: reloading modulus; U^{1st}: first unloading modulus; L: second loading modulus; U^{2nd}: second unloading modulus

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752 **Table 5.** The estimated plastic strain (cumulative) under MSE test

Specimen	CP (MPa)	DS (MPa)	Plastic strain (micro_strain)
R1 (Calcite/quartz-rich)	0	0-15	65
	5	0-15	500
	10	0-15, 0-30	140,440
	20	0-15, 0-30	66,127
	30	0-15, 0-30	8,17
	40	0-15, 0-30	7,46
	50	0-15, 0-30	6,43
R3 (Clay-rich)	0	0-15	28
	5	0-15	333
	10	0-15, 0-30	195,393
	20	0-15, 0-30	139,266
	30	0-15, 0-30	73,151
	40	0-15, 0-30	42,131
	50	0-15, 0-30	58,24

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(a)

(b)

(c)

Test Vessel

(d)

(e)

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